

Some remarks about the Macedonian language

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Some remarks about the Macedonian language*

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The Macedonian literary language is spoken in the Republic of Macedonia, one of the six republics of former S.F.R. Yugoslavia. This standard language was created in the middle of the 20th century, at the end of the World War II. Hence, Macedonian literary language has become one of the youngest member of the family of Slavic literary languages. Historical circumstances did not allow an earlier codification of the Macedonian standard. Ironically, the Macedonian territory where the first Slavic literary language had been founded in the 9th century, the so-called Old Church Slavic language, was the last one to obtain a literary language in the modern sense of meaning.

The Macedonian language has developed among the Slavs that settled to the south from other Slavic tribes. In spite of that, the Macedonian dialects still keep many features that connect the Macedonian area with the neighbouring Slavic languages – Bulgarian and Serbian. In addition, these contact zones have been, through history, areas of irradiation of various political and cultural influences which are reflected in the Macedonian language. The present-day distribution of Macedonian dialects confirms these relations. The southeastern Macedonian dialects, which cross the Macedonian-Bulgarian border, in many linguistic features realize a natural link to the southwest Bulgarian dialects. Dialectal type situated on the north of the Republic of Macedonia is, in fact, a part of the south-Serbian dialectal complex. On the other hand, far from these influences, in the central part of Macedonia (Prilep – Bitola – Veles) a typical Macedonian dialect has been formed.¹

On the wide area of southern Slavic languages there are two main branches of languages. The eastern branch consists of the Bulgarian and Macedonian languages, while the western branch comprises Serbo-Croat and Slovenian. There is a well-known linguistic border which divides these groups of languages, and this linguistic border, of course, does not follow the state borders. For example, the northern dialect of Macedonia (Tetovo – Kumanovo – Kratovo), with dominating Serbian features, belongs to the western group of South Slavic languages (Serbian Svrlijig-Lužnica

* It is a chapter of the article On the Macedonian literary language and its dialectal base, that is presented at linguistic conference in East European and Balkan Institute, Center for International Area Studies - Hankuk University of Foreign Studies (Seoul 2004).

¹ As a part of the western dialect there is a specific narrow peripheral zone located along the Albanian and southwestern Serbian borders.

dialect). Hence, the yers in strong positions have yielded one reflex (e.g. *сън, дън*), the nasal vowel *o* has become an *u* (*рука, нут*), palatals *l'* and *n'* have been preserved (*поље, њива*), feminine nouns ending in plural *-e* (*жене, њиве*), pronouns and adjectives end in *-ga* (*њезга, свакога*), in present tense there are ending *-то* in the 1st person plural (*знамо, идемо*), in word formation there are suffixes *-ić* and *-oća* (*петлић, чистоћа*) etc. (Vidoeski 1998: 95-104). These features are not typical of Macedonian and Bulgarian linguistic zones.

But this, as well as other linguistics traits shows that the Macedonian zone does not belong entirely to the Eastern group of South Slavic languages, and that the linguistic border in its southern zone, between Macedonian and western part of South Slavic languages, is more flexible. That is why some linguistics also point at a gradual dialectal transition between Serbian and Macedonian, which includes a high degree of mutual intelligibility within these zones (*Macedonian: www.lmp.ucla.edu...*).² Blaže Koneski, the famous Macedonian linguist, wrote that “the Macedonian dialects have been a part of the continuum of Serbian and Bulgarian dialects for so long, that today it is not possible to draw distinct boundaries between them” (*Koneski: www.mymacedonia.net/language/modern.htm*). Therefore, there are no linguistic reasons to link Macedonian either with one side only, or to view Macedonian territory as part of Bulgarian dialectal complex. Even Antoine Meillet, the well known linguist comparativist, wrote that Macedonian and Bulgarian dialects have developed a great difference between them (Meje 1965: 40). Why has this happened?

a) First, from the beginning the Macedonian zone was far distanced from the central parts of Bulgarian language and from the direct Bulgarian political influences for a long period. This has enabled the Macedonian language to develop and preserve a series of significant linguistic features. At the same time, the Macedonian language was developing in specific historical circumstances, in a region of manifestly strong contact among the various Balkan languages. The well known Swiss linguist, Ferdinand de Saussure, the founder of linguistic as a modern science, wrote that in Macedonia many languages had been spoken, “Turkish, Bulgarian, Serbian, Greek, Albanian, Aromanian, etc., mixed in different ways from district to district” (Sosir 1996 [1915]: 192). Aromanian and Albanian influences have been especially strong in some parts of Macedonian territory into this day. Although the Macedonian, Bulgarian and some parts of Serbian dialects share many Balkan linguistic features, the so-called Balkanisms,³ owing to its position Macedonian language has developed some Balkanisms of its own, which are not known to the Bulgarian and

² Therefore, there was a notice in one of the grammar books that in Yugoslavia Serbo-Croat “differs considerably from the language of Slovenia, in the north-west, and to a lesser extent from that in Macedonia, in the south-east” (Javarek-Sudjić 1978: XI). Some linguistic planes show this very well (see: Радић 1993).

³ Unlike other Slavic languages, the case system is almost entirely lost, adjectives are compared by using separate prefixes for the comparative and superlative, the infinitive form does not exist anymore, etc.

Serbian dialects. These Balkan characteristic were spread mostly in western Macedonia, in different linguistic levels:

- in the temporal system (e.g. analytic perfect tense with the auxiliary verb "have": *имам читано, имав читано*; see: Gołąb 1959: 416-421);
- in word order and structure of the sentence (e.g. with enclitics at the beginning of the sentence: *те сакам, го гледам, сум болен*; see: Настев 1988: 73-75);
- in word formation (e.g. diminutive suffix *-ule*: *детуле, пилуле, човечуле*; see: Koneski, Vidoeski, Jašar-Nasteva 1968: 523, 528), etc.

These features have secured the Macedonian language a special position among Balkan Slavic languages and due to that in modern linguistics literary Macedonian is usually viewed as the most Balkanized South Slavic language (Илиевски 1988: 13-35). Of course, these Balkan language features have found their place in the contemporary Macedonian literary language too, and just because of that it has made another important difference to Bulgarian literary language.⁴

b) Geographically, the Macedonian territory is especially by the way of the Vardar-Morava valley wide open towards north.⁵ This fact can explain many linguistic phenomena within the framework of Serbian-Macedonian relationship. It can explain some very old Macedonian linguistic features preserved in a series of South Serbian toponyms, as well as many Balkanisms which spread mostly from the Macedonian territory to the central parts of Serbia till today, and which have great influence even on contemporary Serbian literary language (Радић 2003: 130-145). On the other hand, it can also explain not only the Serbian nature of the northern (Slavic) dialect of the Republic of Macedonia, on which border the Macedonian capital Skopje is situated, - but also the series of linguistic features which spread from Serbian and north Macedonian territory through all over the Vardar Macedonia, as early as the middle ages.⁶ It was probably owing to these influences that in a

⁴ In Macedonian literary language stress is placed on the first syllable of bisyllabic words and on the antepenult in words of three or more syllables, definite nouns are indicated by a set of three definite suffixal articles (type: *-ov, -ot, -on*), etc.

⁵ There are some indications which show that contacts between Macedonian and Serbian also used to exist in the zone of nowadays north Albania. Some linguistic data suggest that Slavic dialects from Western Macedonia were in a direct contact with Serbian dialects from southeastern Montenegro until the beginning of the period of Ottoman rule (Радић 1993).

⁶ Some new texts have it that after Macedonian linguistic codification Serbian "and local dialect forms continue to exert an influence on the language, especially those in the Western dialect area, which is the basis for the standard" (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...). Perhaps, we could talk, before all, about influences which directly enter from the Serbian dialect of the Skopje region ("local dialect forms"!?), as capital, into Macedonian literary language (and indirectly into the "Western dialects area"), and after that, in the second place, about influences of "Serbo-Croatian", as principal language of former Yugoslavia. Naturally, after the disintegration of S.F.R. Yugoslavia the former type of influences have continued to exist with the same

major part of central Macedonia ekavian reflex of old vowel 'jat' (see: I), and affricates *k'* (Maced. *ќ*) and *g'* (Maced. *ѓ*) as continuants of Common Slavic consonant groups **tj*, **dj* have been spread or strengthened. A reduced extent of palatal-velar consonant opposition in central Macedonian dialect links this zone with the Serbian dialects too (Белић 1935: 34-52, Ивић 1985²: 16-21, see also: Alexander 2000, maps 5, 13). From this point of view it may be clear why Macedonian Đorđi Puljevski wrote in the 19th century that the Bulgarian language is close to Russian, and on the other hand Macedonian is close to Serbian (see: Пулевски 1974: 97).

This geographic link between Macedonia and Serbia has been a natural background for different relationships between Macedonian and Serbian peoples, and it has influenced many important historical events in Macedonia ever since the middle ages. Not only during the medieval kingdom of Nemanjićs, but also for centuries afterwards, until the 18th century (see: Поп Атанасов 1989), predominant in the Vardar Macedonia was Serbian literary language of medieval type (the Serbian redaction of the Church Slavic language). And after that period there were close cultural connections between the Vardar Macedonia and Serbia. Orthographic reform of the Serb Vuk Karadžić, which offered a simplified graphic system, was very popular in the Vardar Macedonia from the very beginning, which is confirmed by the shape of contemporary graphic system of the Macedonian language. Serbian urban poetry was also well known in Macedonia during the 19th century (Поленакović 1969). Of course, these influences from the Serbian territory have even been intensified in the 20th century when the Vardar Macedonia and Serbia took place in the same state, and when Serbian (once again?) became a language of prestige.

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Macedonian geographic and linguistic position between two Slavic states, Bulgaria and Serbia, has caused in the past not only linguistic (see: Alexander 2000), but also political conflicts among the three sides. There is no consensus especially among Macedonians and Bulgarians, about a series of important linguistic questions regarding the Macedonian language. Even today, for example, Macedonian is viewed in Bulgaria as one of the Bulgarian dialects (Български диалектен атлас... 2001), while on the other hand Macedonian dialectologists view the dialect of Bulgarian Pirin as a dialect of the Macedonian language.⁷ Although Macedonian is considered in Bulgaria as a 'regional norm' of Bulgarian (see: Единството на българския език... 1978: 14, 33), the Macedonian language

intensity. It is well shown in some recent Macedonian texts where even an aversion to this dialect is expressed (Спировски 2002: 64). On the other hand, a cultural influence from Serbia could not be stopped after Macedonian separation either (see footnote 11).

⁷ There are also citizens and emigrants from Bulgaria who "identify their native (Slavonic) language as Macedonian" (*Macedonian Language*: www.macedonia.co.uk./mcic...).

and Macedonian publications are outlawed in Bulgaria today (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...).⁸ Taking part in this linguistic conflict there are also some foreign intellectuals, unfortunately sometimes not free of certain political inspirations - they usually act according to their personal attitude to the various nations of the Balkan, and lately especially to the last civil war in Yugoslavia. So, although the majority of foreign linguists do recognize the Macedonian identity (e.g. Friedman 1985, Friedman 1999), some of them discuss the matter from a Bulgarian point of view (e.g. Carmichael 2000),⁹ while there are also foreign authors who observe this matter from a Serbian point of view (e.g. Stojanović 1997,¹⁰ see also: Pajc 1918, Pajc 1998 [1928]²).

Theoretically, due to many linguistic similarities, the Macedonian people could build their literary language together with the Bulgarian people (or they could just accept Bulgarian standard). Macedonians could also build their literary language together with the Serbian people (or simply accept the Serbian standard), due to many rich cultural and linguistic interactions which have lasted for centuries, into this day.¹¹ But historical circumstances in the Vardar Macedonia have paved the third way to Macedonian people, and enabled them to establish their own state and to build their own literary language on the basis of one of the Macedonian dialects. The question what will happen in the future, does not belong to science.

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⁸ On the other hand, in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, between world wars, Macedonian literature was tolerated as "local dialectal folkloric form" (*Macedonian*: www.lmp.ucla.edu...). This position enabled some continuum to Macedonian literature and culture.

⁹ It's very simplified, and even wrong approach who emphasizes: „As a language, Macedonian is *very similar to Bulgarian*, but historically, since Serbia has been *a stronger and more aggressive state than Bulgaria* [P.R.], Macedonia, and consequently its language, developed separately from Bulgaria, particularly since Macedonia's annexation by Serbia in 1912" (Carmichael 2000: 229). Macedonian "similarity" to Bulgarian (or Serbian) certainly doesn't mean that Macedonian have to accept Bulgarian (or Serbian) literary language. Situation after disintegration of "Serbo-Croatian" language shows this very well. In addition, it would be certainly controversial attitude to name as "aggressive" the state which was among victors in two world wars, differ to Bulgaria, for example. (About last events in Yugoslavia history didn't say its last word yet.)

¹⁰ American professor of Macedonian origin, Trajan Stojanović, wrote that Macedonian literary language was just result of political projections by Yugoslav Marxists (Stojanović 1997: 339).

¹¹ Serbian cultural and linguistic presence in Vardar Macedonia, as what could be expected, didn't stop after the Macedonian separatism. Therefore, it caused claims among some linguists for some kind of Macedonian cultural isolations from the northern neighbour (Минова-Гуркова 2004).

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<Summary>

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Theoretically, due to many linguistic similarities, the Macedonian people could build their literary language together with the Bulgarian people (or they could just accept Bulgarian standard). Macedonians could also build their literary language together with the Serbian people (or simply accept the Serbian standard), due to many rich cultural and linguistic interactions which have lasted for centuries, into this day. But historical circumstances in the Vardar Macedonia have paved the third way to Macedonian people, and enabled them to establish their own state and to build their own literary language on the basis of one of the Macedonian dialects. The Macedonian central dialect is

distanced from both the Bulgarian and Serbian dialectal centers and has its own special linguistic features.

<Key words>

Macedonian, Bulgarian, Serbian, Standard language, Dialect

<주제어>

마케도니아어, 불가리아어, 세르비아어, 표준어, 방언

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